

Effect of Gamma Irradiation on HT, 5HT and HT + AET in in-vitro System

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5-Hydroxy-L-tryptophan (HT) and 5-hydroxytryptamine (5HT) in aqueous solution show steady decrease in absorption intensities at 207, 275 and 222 nm with decrease in pH in the dose range of 100–1500 Gy. The absorbance ratios at all these wavelengths indicate that HT is much less sensitive to breakdown by gamma irradiation as compared to that of 5HT.

IR spectral studies of HT and 5HT indicates that upon gamma irradiation (i) deamination takes place from both the compounds but from the side-chain it is more with 5HT, (ii) decarboxylation takes place from HT, (iii) intermolecular hydrogen bonding takes place through 5-hydroxyl group for both the compounds which gets deformed upon irradiation and (iv) cleavage of the double bond in the β -carbon atom in both the compounds takes place.

A consistent decrease of pH is observed with increasing gamma irradiation for HT and 2-aminoethylisothiuronium bromide hydrobromide (AET). But for HT + AET the variation of pH with radiation dose is biphasic.

IR spectral studies on the effect of gamma irradiation on HT + AET indicates that (i) the C–S–C linkage of AET get distorted, (ii) the amide bond is vulnerable to disruption, (iii) there is a disruption in the unsaturation of β -carbon atom and (iv) perturbation and stretching of =NH, -NH₂ and H₂N–C=NH take place with gamma radiation dose.

Radioprotective efficacies in biological systems are dependent on certain functional groups of chemical radioprotectors and their spatial disposition with respect to different tissues or cells which get radioprotection^{1–6}.

Effects of gamma irradiation on 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan (HT), 5-hydroxytryptamine (5HT) and HT + AET (2-aminoethylisothiuronium bromide hydrobromide) have been studied in in-vitro system by following uv and ir spectra alongwith pH changes due to gamma irradiation.

Results and Discussion

Figs. 1 and 2 depict the uv absorption spectra of HT and 5HT in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states. The absorption of HT at 275 nm is due to the side-chain $-\text{CH}-\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)-\text{COOH}$ ⁷.

The difference in absorption values of HT and 5HT at 275 nm is due to the difference in side-chain present in these two compounds. The absorption at 207 nm is due to the pyrrole group present in HT and 5HT. The shoulder at 220 nm is due to the indole ring⁸. The differences in the intensities of absorption for 5HT compared to HT at 220 and 207 nm are also probable due to the difference in the terminal side-chain COOH group.

Table 1 shows the relative absorption values of HT (i.e. unirradiated : irradiated) and 5HT at different doses and the corresponding pH values.

With increase in gamma irradiation dose there is a marked decrease in the absorption at 207 and 220 nm for both HT and 5HT solutions. This indicates that indole/pyrrole rings of the compounds are affected by gamma irradiation. It is also reported⁹

Fig. 1. Uv absorption spectra of HT in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states at concn. $90.82 \mu M$: (o) unirradiated, pH 6.05 (●) 100 Gy, pH 5.83, (x) 300 Gy, pH 5.55 (▲) 500 Gy, pH 5.01, (O) 1000 Gy, pH 4.72, and (⊙) 1500 Gy, pH 4.59.

Fig. 2. Uv absorption spectra of 5HT in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states at concn. $90.82 \mu M$: (o) unirradiated, pH 5.80 (●) 100 Gy, pH 5.60, (x) 300 Gy, pH 5.09 (▲) 500 Gy, pH 5.06, (O) 1000 Gy, pH 4.89, and (⊙) 1500 Gy, pH 4.74.

that hydroxyl radical is responsible for the breakdown of indole and pyrrole rings of HT and 5HT.

TABLE I—RELATIVE ABSORPTION VALUES (UNIRRADIATED IRRADIATED) OF IIT AND 5HT AT DIFFERENT DOSES

Dose Gy	Absorbance ratio (A_{unirr}/A_{irr}) at			pH
	207 nm HT	220 nm	275 nm	
Concn of HT/5HT = $90.82 \mu M$				
Unirr	1.00	1.00	1.00	6.05
100	1.08	1.01	1.00	5.83
300	1.08	1.19	1.06	5.55
500	1.22	1.40	1.10	5.01
1000	1.41	1.90	1.14	4.72
1500	1.50	2.27	1.20	4.58
5HT				
Unirr	1.00	1.00	1.00	5.80
100	1.08	1.13	1.17	5.60
300	1.19	1.43	1.37	5.09
500	1.25	1.72	1.52	5.06
1000	1.66	2.14	1.81	4.89
1500	1.78	2.24	1.87	4.74

There is a consistent decrease of pH with increasing dose of gamma irradiation for both HT and 5HT. For a minimum dose of 1500 Gy the decrease in pH is 1.47 for HT and 1.06 for 5HT. The decrease of pH is attributed to decarboxylation¹⁰ as a result of gamma irradiation. Decarboxylation is possible from the pyrrole ring in both the compounds. In case of HT some additional decarboxylation seems to have taken place from the side-chain and thus the decrease in pH is more for HT. Absorbance ratios are less for HT than 5HT at all wavelengths with any particular irradiation dose. This clearly shows that HT is much less sensitive to breakdown by gamma irradiation as compared to that of 5HT.

Deamination at the α -carbon position is a relatively easier process. In the radiolysis of aromatic amino acids $G(NH_3) < 0.5$ in both the evacuated and oxygenated solutions of tryptophan¹¹. Thus minor changes have been noted at 275 nm with radiation dose for both HT and 5HT. Changes in 5HT solution is greater as compared to that in HT solution at 275 nm indicating that the terminal chain is better protected due to the presence of COOH group.

IR spectral features of HT and 5HT are presented in Table 2. At 3400 cm^{-1} the percentage absorbance difference from unirradiated to irradiated is 8% for HT. Moreover, the doublet that is observed before irradiation is no more present after irradiation¹². This indicates decarboxylation from side-chain of HT to a slight extent¹³. The zwitterion that was present in the irradiated HT gets dissociated first and then decarboxylation takes place as a result of gamma irradiation. This indicates that deamination from side-chain is only possible when the amino group is free. So, compared to HT, 5HT will induce more deamination upon gamma irradiation. From 1150 to 1050 cm^{-1} there is a difference of 8 to 12% in percentage absorbance from unirradiated to irradiated HT, depending upon wavenumber. This indicates C–OH linkage of 5-hydroxyl group of HT and its subsequent deformation upon irradiation¹⁴. Probably the intermolecular hydrogen bonding through 5-hydroxyl group is disrupted by gamma irradiation. The two adjacent free hydrogen atoms in the benzene ring has been shown at 850 cm^{-1} for HT in the unirradiated and irradiated states¹⁵.

All these results refers to Table 2. At 3480 and 3250 cm^{-1} the difference in the percentage absorbance from unirradiated to irradiated 5HT is 10. It indicates slight deamination from side-chain¹⁶. But its intensity is not high as $G(\text{NH}_3) < 0.5$ in both evacuated and oxygenated solution of tryptophan¹⁷. Ammonia liberation by gamma irradiation from 5HT has been confirmed experimentally. At 2100 cm^{-1} there is a peak for 5HT in the unirradiated state which upon irradiation is not observed. This may indicate the presence of $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ (usual position 2240 – 2220 cm^{-1}). From 1580 to 1500 cm^{-1} there is a difference in the percentage absorbance from unirradiated to irradiated 5HT. This can be attributed to NH deformation mode¹⁸ for a secondary amide formation. From the comparison of the two spectra of 5HT (irradiated and unirradiated) at 1300 cm^{-1} it is observed that there is a sharp peak for unirradiated and no peak for irradiated one. This indicates of a β -cleavage between second and third carbon atom with respect to NH group of pyrrole¹⁹. At 1090 cm^{-1} there is a difference of

20% in the percentage absorbance of 5HT. It indicates disruption of intermolecular hydrogen bonding of 5HT through 5-hydroxyl group as mentioned for HT also. The difference in percentage absorbance at 900 cm^{-1} is due to olefinic hydrogen (*trans*). Upon irradiation intensity of this absorption is reduced considerably indicating thereby that upon absorption of energy from gamma rays some *trans* compounds get converted to *cis*. It is further observed that the peak at 670 cm^{-1} for the unirradiated 5HT which is attributed to *cis*-olefinic hydrogen almost disappears upon irradiation. This interconversion of *cis* to *trans* is energetically favourable. But the opposite is not true²⁰. The two adjacent free hydrogen atoms in the benzene ring has been shown at 850 cm^{-1} for 5HT in the unirradiated and irradiated states²¹. All these results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF IIT AND 5IIT IN THE UNIRRADIATED AND GAMMA IRRADIATED STATES

Wavenumber cm^{-1}	IIT		5-IIT	
	Unirr %A	Irr %A	Unirr %A	Irr %A
3480	—	—	78	68
3400	83	75	—	—
3250	—	—	70	60
2100	—	—	82	Peak absent
1580	—	—	67	Peak absent
1560	—	—	54	69
1500	—	—	56	73
1490	57	66	—	—
1470	57	65	—	—
1410	51	56	—	—
1300	—	—	59	Peak absent
1150	75	83	—	—
1090	—	—	34	54
1050	74	86	—	—
980	78	87	—	—
930	79	90	50	85
900	—	—	50	90
850	60	73	50	87
800	—	—	47	85
670	—	—	40	93

Ir spectral studies on HT and 5HT indicate that (a) deamination takes place from both the compounds upon gamma irradiation, but from side-chain it is more with 5HT, (b) decarboxylation

takes place from HT upon gamma irradiation, (c) intermolecular hydrogen bonding takes place through 5-hydroxyl group for both the compounds which gets deformed upon irradiation, and (d) as a result of gamma irradiation cleavage of the double bond in the β -carbon atom occurs in both the compounds.

Table 3 shows the variation in pH with gamma radiation dose of AET, HT and HT + AET. For both HT and AET there is a consistent decrease of pH with gamma radiation dose up to 1500 Gy. But HT + AET behaves in a different manner where the variation of pH with radiation dose is biphasic.

TABLE 3—pH OF RADIOPROTECTORS AND THEIR MIXTURES AS A FUNCTION OF GAMMA IRRADIATION DOSE

Compd / Concn (μ M)	Unirradiated	Gamma irradiated (Gy)			
		100	300	500	1500
HT					
90 82	6 05	5 83	5 55	5 01	4 58
AET					
14 23	3 85	3 65	3 38	3 11	3 05
HT + AET					
90 82 + 14 23	5 20	5 45	5 50	5 37	4 91

Gamma radiation induced reactions of HT and AET are presented in Scheme 1 and Scheme 2 respectively.

Scheme 1

The initial increase of pH for HT + AET upto 300 Gy is likely to be due to formation of NH_4OH from ammonia liberated from side-chain of HT and $=\text{NH}$ group of AET of the complex. Afterwards with further increase in radiation dose, the complex breaks down producing ionisable carboxyl groups both from HT and AET causing the pH to decrease.

Scheme 2

The ir spectral studies on the effect of different doses of gamma irradiation on HT + AET have been depicted in Table 4. It is observed that in all wavenumbers there is increase in percentage absorbance with increase in dose except at 1650 cm^{-1} . The variation in percentage absorbance at 650 cm^{-1} is due to distortion in the C-S-C linkage of AET with variation in dose²² and the variation at 1000 cm^{-1} is due to variation in the C-O stretching vibration of 5-OH of HT²³. There is an irregular variation in percentage absorbance at 1650 cm^{-1} with dose. This indicates that the amide bond is vulnerable to disruption with gamma radiation. Moreover, it indicates that the unsaturation of carbon atom of HT gets disturbed on complex formation and its value further changes with radiation dose²³

The wavenumber range of $3000\text{--}3550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is for $=\text{NH}$ stretching mode, side-chain NH_2 and $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{NH}$. Perturbation and stretching of all of these functional groups with gamma radiation dose is envisaged²⁴.

Experimental

HT, 5HT and AET (Sigma) were used. The compounds were dissolved in water on warming slightly to about 37° . The absorbance of the solutions of HT and 5HT were studied spectrophotometrically in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states for a dose range of 100–1500 Gy. The dose rate was 0.077 Gy/s for irradiation of the solutions of these two compounds²⁵. pH measurements of all the experimental solutions were carried out in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states.

TABLE 4—PERCENTAGE ABSORBANCE VALUES AT DIFFERENT WAVENUMBERS OF HT + AET IN THE UNIRRADIATED AND DIFFERENTLY GAMMA IRRADIATED STATES

Wave number cm^{-1}	HT + AET(%A) (Unirradiated)	HT + AET 5Gy (%A)	HT + AET 10 Gy (%A)	HT + AET 15 Gy (%A)	Assignment*
650	21.5	38	50	55	A
750	—	—	—	—	
1000	35	45.5	50	57.5	B
1150	31	47	64	—	—
1500	64	—	—	—	—
1650	98	49	60.0	64.5	C
2850	—	—	—	—	—
2900	—	—	—	—	—
3000–3550	26	38	50.5	54	D

* A = distortion in the C–S–C linkage with variation in radiation dose. B = variation in the C–O stretching vibration of 5-OH of HT. C = unsaturation of β -carbon atom of HT gets disturbed on complex formation; the value further changes with radiation dose. D = NH_2^+ of HT and AET are involved in complex formation. The characteristic absorption in this region is for NH stretching mode, side-chain $-\text{NH}_2$, $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{NH}$. Perturbation and stretching of all of these functional groups with gamma radiation dose is envisaged.

Spectrophotometric observations were made by a Carl-Zeiss PMQ II spectrophotometer. Gamma irradiations were done in a Gamma cell 220 of Atomic Energy of Canada.

For ir spectral studies HT, 5HT and HT + AET (concn. 10 mg ml^{-1}) were lyophilised at -30° and a pressure of 6 m bar for 6 h. Gamma irradiation was done to any desired dose (1500 Gy for HT and 5HT and 5, 10 and 15 Gy for HT + AET) for a particular compound in solution before lyophilisation. The dose rate was 2.6 Gy/min with a transit dose of 0.32 Gy^{25} . These were then pelleted with KBr, made a thin film and ir spectra obtained. A Perkin-Elmer equipment was used for ir spectral studies.

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References

1. J. RENSON, *Arch. Int. Physiol. Biochem.*, 1960, **68**, 531.
2. C. STREFFER, H. LANGENDORFF and U. ALBERT, *Strahlentherapie*, 1960, **135**, 76.
3. J. RENSON and P. FISHER, *Arch. Int. Physiol. Biochem.*, 1959, **67**, 142.
4. G. SCHLOES, P. SHAW, R. L. WILSON and M. EBERT in "Pulse Radiolysis". ed. M. EBERT, Academic, London, 1965, p. 151.
5. W. KARSTEN and A. MUBER, *Int. J. Rad. Biol.*, 1981, **39**, 235.
6. M. L. GARRIOT and D. T. GROWE, *Radiat. Res.*, 1983, **93**, 200.
7. J. W. SIDMAN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1958, **58**, 689.
8. C. N. R. RAO, "Ultraviolet and Visible Spectroscopy, Chemical Applications", Butterworths, London, 1967, p. 77.
9. J. RENSON, *J. Physiol.*, 1960, **52**, 208.
10. S. N. UPADHYAY, R. P. SINGH, A. K. GUPTA and A. GHOSE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 560.
11. P. ALEXANDER and D. ROSEN, *Nature (London)*, 1960, **188**, 574.
12. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Chapman Hall, London, 1975, p. 226.
13. C. A. JOINSTON, K. D. FAGIN, P. H. ALPER and A. N. VILAR, *Endocrinology*, 1986, **18**, 805.
14. Ref. 12, p. 108.
15. Ref. 12, p. 74.
16. Ref. 12, p. 273.
17. Ref. 12, p. 184.
18. Ref. 12, p. 244.
19. Ref. 12, p. 38.
20. T. N. SORREL, "Interpreting Spectra of Organic Molecules", University Science Books, Hill Valley, p. 19.
21. Ref. 20, p. 48.
22. Ref. 20, p. 35.
23. J. THOMPSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 320.
24. J. THOMPSON, NICHOLSON and SHORT, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1950, **9**, 222.
25. H. FRICKE and S. MORSE, *Phil. Mag.*, 1929, **7**, 129.

